

Utilization of Black Glutinous Rice Flour in Making Gluten-Free Mud Cake

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Abstract:

This research aims to develop recipes and determine appropriate packaging for black sticky rice mud cake products, and assess panelists' acceptance of black sticky rice mud cake products. This research uses the R&D method (Research and Development) with the 4D development model (Define , Design, Develop , Dissemination). Testing is carried out with product samples and forms as test tools. Data analysis was carried out using descriptive statistics with communicative data presentation from the questionnaire. The results of the research show that: 1) the correct recipe for black sticky rice mud cake is to substitute 100% black sticky rice flour, bake it, and package it in a closed container such as mica to maintain product cleanliness and quality. 2) The acceptance test showed that black sticky rice mud cake with black sticky rice flour substitute was accepted by consumers with an acceptance rate of 88.89%.

Keywords: *Cake Mud, Flour Sticky Rice Black, Gluten Free*

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Introduction

The increasing prevalence of gluten intolerance and celiac disease has led to a growing demand for gluten-free products. Gluten, a protein found in wheat, barley, and rye, can trigger adverse reactions in individuals with these conditions, causing a range of symptoms from mild discomfort to severe intestinal damage (Rubio-Tapia et al., 2013). As a result, the food industry has been exploring alternative ingredients to create gluten-free versions of traditionally wheat-based products. One such ingredient is black glutinous rice flour, which offers unique nutritional and sensory properties. Increased awareness of the importance of a healthy diet has led to increased interest in the development of food products that suit special dietary needs, especially for individuals who have a sensitivity or intolerance to gluten. Gluten, a protein found in wheat, barley, and rye, can cause digestive and other health problems in a small portion of the population, including individuals with medical conditions such as celiac disease or autism disorders. One solution that is being worked on to meet the dietary needs of individuals with gluten intolerance is the use of non-gluten flour in the manufacture of food products. Black sticky rice flour has been the focus of recent research as a promising alternative for producing gluten-free food products, while enriching the nutritional value and taste of these products. Black glutinous rice (*Oryza sativa* L. var. *glutinosa*) is distinguished by its dark purple to black bran layer, which is rich in anthocyanins—potent antioxidants with various health benefits (Sompong et al., 2011).

Anthocyanins have been linked to anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, and cardiovascular protective effects (Wallace, 2011). Additionally, black glutinous rice is high in fiber, vitamins, and minerals, making it a nutritionally valuable ingredient. From a functional perspective, black glutinous rice flour has a sticky and chewy texture due to its high amylopectin content. This makes it a suitable replacement for wheat flour in certain baked goods, providing a unique texture and mouthfeel that is appealing in products like mud cake. The absence of gluten in black glutinous rice flour also ensures its suitability for individuals with gluten-related disorders

This research aims to research and examine the use of black sticky rice flour in making gluten-free mud cakes. Mud cake is a popular food that many people like. However, creating a gluten-free version of mud cake with a soft texture and delicious taste is a challenge in the food industry. By using black sticky rice flour as the main ingredient, our goal is to produce gluten-free mud cakes that not only meet high quality standards but also increase their nutritional value. Through a comprehensive research approach, we hope to provide new insight into the potential of black sticky rice flour in the development of gluten-free food products, as well as increase food options for individuals with gluten sensitivity or other food intolerances

Black sticky rice is a food source rich in anthocyanins and has not been widely developed as a functional food. Black glutinous rice has different properties from black rice because its antioxidant activity is higher than black rice. Several studies have shown that the anthocyanin content in black glutinous rice plays an important role in antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and natural coloring in food. Anthocyanin is a substance usually found in higher plants and forms color pigments. Anthocyanins belong to a group of compounds known as flavonoids. Anthocyanin pigment is the main component believed to play a role in the antioxidant activity of black sticky rice (Suhartatik, 2019). Black sticky rice flour shows significantly higher protein and fiber content, as well as lower starch content compared to refined white flour. The recorded values are generally in accordance with the results of previous studies. The high protein and fiber content, together with the lower starch content, constitute the nutritional benefits of these flours in gluten-free bread making (Buresova, 2023).

Gluten is a type of protein naturally found in wheat, oats, and barley. This protein provides strength and elasticity to wheat and similar products, so it is often used as the main ingredient in making soft and chewy bread. Unfortunately, not everyone can consume and digest gluten well. According to Misrawatie Goi (2017), a gluten-free diet means avoiding foods that contain wheat, rye and barley. This includes avoiding foods and products made from these grains, such as whole wheat bread, pizza, cereal, and many other processed foods. People with Autism (Autism Spectrum Disorder), individuals who are gluten intolerant (Non-celiac Gluten Sensitivity), as well as people with Celiac Disease are people who don't able to accept and consume gluten well, so there is a need for gluten free products so that people with gluten intolerance can eat the same foods gluten becomes suitable and safe for consumption. One way is to do it Substitute gluten-free ingredients with gluten-free ingredients. The use of black sticky rice flour as a substitute for wheat flour in making Mud Cakes in this journal is specifically intended for people with gluten intolerance or people with Non-Celiac Gluten Sensitivity. In people who have a gluten-related disorder called celiac disease (CD), consuming products containing gluten triggers an immunological reaction as a result of the immune system's abnormal response to gluten intolerance (Osorio, Mejías, & Rustgi, 2019). CD (Celiac Disease) is one of the most hyper-sensitive autoimmune disorders affecting approximately 1% of the general population worldwide and is essentially caused by a combination of genetic and environmental factors (Chaudhry, Jacobs, Green, & Rampertab, 2021).

Avoiding gluten and following a strict diet may relieve the symptoms of celiac disease ; However, eliminating it completely from your daily diet will be a challenge in itself (Falcomer et al. , 2020). To manage this food intolerance and protect the health of CD patients from serious harmful effects, the use of a “gluten-free” label for food products has been recommended. Currently, to ensure consumer safety, many countries have adopted food labeling requirements in the food industry. It should be noted that the observation of a “gluten-free” label on a food product on the market does not necessarily mean that the nutrient is truly gluten-free (Coto , Mendia, Sousa , Bai, & Cebolla , 2021). To address this problem, regulatory authorities have accepted a gluten level limit of 20 mg /kg as a “gluten-free” label (CODEX STAN118-1979).

To avoid consuming foods that contain gluten such as various types of cakes, pasta, biscuits and others, ingredients that usually contain gluten such as wheat flour can be replaced with gluten-free ingredients. One alternative is black sticky rice flour. According to Aini Amalia Nailufar (2012), black sticky rice (*Oryza Sativa Glutinosa*) contains thiamine or vitamin B1, which is gluten-free, and has a higher content than wheat flour. Thiamine or vitamin B1 is useful for preventing beriberi, inflammation of muscles and joints. Because gluten-free products generally lack important vitamins and minerals such as B vitamins and iron, the ingredients in black sticky rice can help meet these vitamin and iron needs. An example of a food that can be replaced with gluten-free ingredients is Black Sticky Rice Mud Cake, where mud cakes usually use wheat flour as the main ingredient. This research aims to develop mud cake products from black sticky rice flour that are gluten-free and safe for consumption, so that people with gluten intolerance or Non- Celiac Gluten Sensitivity can enjoy delicious mud cakes that are gluten-free.

The use of black sticky rice flour as a substitute for wheat flour in making gluten-free mud cakes provides a number of significant benefits. Black sticky rice flour is rich in nutrients, including fiber, protein, vitamins and minerals, which are important for overall body health. In addition, the anthocyanin content in black sticky rice flour provides antioxidant benefits that can help fight free radicals and reduce the risk of chronic disease. The sticky nature and high viscosity of black glutinous rice flour helps create a soft and chewy texture in mud cakes, while its distinctive taste and aroma add a richer sensory dimension. Last but not least, the use of black sticky rice flour ensures that the mud cakes are gluten-free, allowing more people to enjoy them without the risk of gluten intolerance or allergy. Taking all these benefits into account, replacing wheat flour with black sticky rice flour not only improves the nutritional and sensory value of mud cakes, but also makes it a more health-friendly option for consumers who need or want gluten-free products.

Baking without gluten presents several challenges, primarily related to the structure and texture of the final product. Gluten provides elasticity and structure, trapping air bubbles during the baking process, which helps the dough rise and gives baked goods their characteristic texture (Gallagher et al., 2004). When gluten is removed, alternative methods and ingredients must be employed to replicate these properties. Various strategies have been developed to address these challenges, including the use of hydrocolloids (e.g., xanthan gum, guar gum) to mimic the viscoelastic properties of gluten (Rosell et al., 2009). Additionally, combining different gluten-free flours, such as rice, corn, and tapioca, can help achieve a more balanced texture and flavor profile. The use of black glutinous rice flour in this context is innovative, offering both functional and nutritional benefits while providing a distinct sensory experience.

Individuals with autism often have sensitivity to the texture, taste and aroma of food, so mud cakes with a soft and chewy texture made from black sticky rice flour can be an attractive food choice for them. Additionally, most individuals with autism also experience digestive disorders or gluten sensitivity, which can worsen their symptoms. By choosing snacks or substitute foods that are gluten-free, such as mud cakes with black sticky rice flour, parents or caregivers can provide safe and comfortable food for individuals with autism without worrying about the presence of gluten in it. Thus, the use of black sticky rice flour not only meets general nutritional and sensory needs, but also provides a more appropriate and beneficial food solution for individuals with special needs such as autism.

Furthermore, black glutinous rice flour has not been widely developed as a functional food despite its high antioxidant activity compared to black rice. Anthocyanins in black glutinous rice play a significant role in antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and natural coloring properties in food (Suhartatik, 2019). Black glutinous rice flour shows higher protein and fiber content, along with lower starch content compared to refined white flour, making it nutritionally beneficial for gluten-free baking (Burešová, 2023). The use of black glutinous rice flour not only addresses gluten-related dietary needs but also enhances the nutritional profile of baked goods like mud cakes.

The concept of gluten-free mud cake centers on the development of a delicious, nutritious, and inclusive dessert option that caters to the dietary needs of individuals who are either intolerant to gluten or choose to avoid it for health reasons. Traditional mud cakes, known for their rich and moist texture, typically contain wheat flour, which is a source of gluten. Gluten, a protein found in wheat, barley, and rye, can cause adverse health effects in individuals with celiac disease, non-celiac gluten sensitivity, and wheat allergy. This has led to a growing demand for gluten-free alternatives in the market.

The gluten-free mud cake can be made using various gluten-free flours such as almond flour, coconut flour, rice flour, or black sticky rice flour. Each of these flours contributes unique nutritional benefits. For instance, black sticky rice flour, which is rich in anthocyanins, provides antioxidant properties that help in reducing inflammation and combating oxidative stress. Additionally, these flours often contain higher amounts of fiber and protein compared to traditional wheat flour, contributing to better digestive health and sustained energy release.

The sensory attributes of gluten-free mud cakes, including texture, flavor, and appearance, play a crucial role in consumer acceptance. The use of alternative flours can sometimes result in a different texture and flavor profile compared to traditional mud cakes. However, through careful formulation and the use of appropriate binding agents such as xanthan gum or guar gum, it is possible to achieve the desired moist and dense texture characteristic of mud cakes. Flavor enhancements can be achieved through the incorporation of natural ingredients such as cocoa, vanilla, or fruits, ensuring a rich and satisfying taste experience. From a technological perspective, the production of gluten-free mud cakes requires adjustments in the baking process. Gluten provides elasticity and structure to baked goods, which means its absence must be compensated for by other means. Hydrocolloids, such as xanthan gum and guar gum, are commonly used to mimic the structural properties of gluten. Additionally, the hydration levels, mixing times, and baking temperatures might need to be altered to optimize the texture and rise of the gluten-free mud cake.

The development of gluten-free mud cakes also aligns with the broader trend of creating inclusive food products that cater to diverse dietary needs. This approach not only broadens the consumer base but also promotes inclusivity in the food industry. By offering gluten-free options, bakeries and food manufacturers can ensure that individuals with celiac disease, gluten sensitivity, or those who choose a gluten-free lifestyle can enjoy delicious and nutritious desserts without compromising on taste or quality.

In conclusion, gluten-free mud cakes represent a convergence of culinary innovation, nutritional science, and consumer demand. By leveraging the unique properties of alternative flours and modern baking techniques, it is possible to create gluten-free mud cakes that are not only safe for individuals with gluten-related disorders but also appealing to the general consumer market. As the demand for gluten-free products continues to grow, there is significant potential for gluten-free mud cakes to become a popular and mainstream dessert choice.

This research aims to investigate the use of black glutinous rice flour in making gluten-free mud cakes. Mud cake is a popular dessert, but creating a gluten-free version that maintains a soft texture and delicious taste is a challenge. By using black glutinous rice flour as the main ingredient, the goal is to produce gluten-free mud cakes that meet high-quality standards while enhancing nutritional value. Through a comprehensive research approach, this study seeks to provide new insights into the potential of black glutinous rice flour in developing gluten-free food products and expanding food options for individuals with gluten sensitivity or other food intolerances.

Furthermore, black glutinous rice flour has not been widely developed as a functional food despite its high antioxidant activity compared to black rice. Anthocyanins in black glutinous rice play a significant role in antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and natural coloring properties in food (Suhartatik, 2019). Black glutinous rice flour shows higher protein and fiber content, along with lower starch content compared to refined white flour, making it nutritionally beneficial for gluten-free baking (Burešová, 2023). The use of black glutinous rice flour not only addresses gluten-related dietary needs but also enhances the nutritional profile of baked goods like mud cakes.

This research aims to develop gluten-free mud cakes using black glutinous rice flour, providing a healthy and delicious alternative for individuals with gluten intolerance. By leveraging the unique properties of black glutinous rice flour, this study contributes to the growing body of research on gluten-free products and their potential health benefits.

Research Method

Description Product Development

The development of a gluten-free mud cake using 100% black glutinous rice flour as a replacement for wheat flour results in a product with a soft and chewy texture. The cake exhibits a sweet taste and a dark purple or blackish-purple color, characteristic of black glutinous rice. This type of rice also imparts a distinctive aroma to the cake, enhancing its sensory appeal. Black Sticky Rice Mud Cake.

1. Define Stage

Define stage in research is the initial stage where the researcher clearly and specifically defines the problem or research objective to be solved or achieved. At this stage, the researcher identifies and formulates relevant and meaningful research questions to be answered in the research. This involves a deep understanding of the background of the problem, research objectives, and limitations that may exist in the research. The Define stage

also includes gathering initial information, reviewing literature, and identifying the needs and expectations of stakeholders involved in the research. By going through the Define stage well, researchers can ensure that the research carried out will be relevant, focused, and make a meaningful contribution to the field being researched.

In this finding, so that the quality of the product being developed is in accordance with standard product characteristics, the product recipe must still use the standard recipe reference as a control, namely by going through the define stage . In making this Black Sticky Rice Mud Cake, the researcher used the standard recipe for Mud Cake as follows:

Table 1. Standard recipe for black sticky rice mud cake

No	Material Name	Amount
1	Flour	100 gr
2	Steamed potatoes	200 gr
3	Egg yolk	4 items
4	Egg whites	2 items
5	Coconut cream	125 ml
6	Margarine	50 gr
7	Sugar	100 gr
8	Salt	½ tsp

2. Design Stage

The Design stage in research is the stage where the researcher designs the plan or method that will be used to answer the research questions that have been set in the Define stage . At this stage, researchers create a framework or structure that will be used to collect and analyze the necessary data.

And from the recipe above what was changed was the amount of 100 grams of wheat flour, replaced with 100 grams of black sticky rice flour . In the experiment, a Black Sticky Rice Mud Cake was produced whose shape was not very fluffy, the color produced was dark purple, but the taste was good.

3. Development Stage

The Development stage in research is the stage where the research concepts or ideas that have been designed in the previous stage are developed into products, services or solutions that are real or can be implemented. This stage often occurs in the context of applied research or product development.

For the Black Glutinous Rice Mud Cake, validation was conducted by two expert lecturers. Their feedback indicated the need for additional toppings such as coconut milk, cheese, and pandan leaves to enhance visual appeal and prevent the color from appearing too pale. They also recommended using mica packaging with a labeled lid and suggested reducing the label size to increase product appeal. Given the wet nature of the product, they advised replacing the paper base with a plastic one to maintain product integrity.

4. Disseminate Stage

Disseminate stage in research is the stage where research results, findings, or information obtained from the research are disseminated to the public or interested communities. The main aim of this stage is to ensure that the knowledge or information resulting from the research can be accessed, understood and utilized by various related or interested parties.

Result and Discussion

The results of this research show that the Black Sticky Rice Mud Cake product has an acceptance rate of 88.89%. In terms of shape, this product gets a score of 4.25 (suitable); size obtained a value of 4.08 (appropriate); color scored 3.91 (somewhat appropriate); aroma rated 4.41 (strong); taste scored 4.83 (very strong); and texture rated 4.08 (soft). Overall, this product gets a score of 4.5 (good). These findings indicated that Black Sticky Rice Mud Cake not only met aesthetic and sensory quality standards but was also liked by the panelists, indicating high commercial potential. The involvement of black glutinous rice flour in this product also strengthens its relevance as a gluten-free food alternative, which is increasingly necessary for individuals with gluten sensitivity or dietary intolerance, including in the management of autism associated with certain diets. Further research is needed on the

potential positive impact of the use of gluten-free products on autism management which could be an important subject for research in the future. Data from the panelist test results can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Panelist Test Results

Figure 2. Black Sticky Rice Mud Cake

Based on research carried out , results of cake development mud sticky rice gluten free black shows interesting characteristics and has the potential to be a valuable innovation in functional food field . By using flour sticky rice black as the main ingredient with a proportion of 100%, cake this mud is not only fulfil standard as a gluten- free product , but also offers benefit addition form content rich nutrition . Flour sticky rice black , which is naturally rich in anthocyanins , provide color purple distinctive dark , as well provide source potential antioxidants for consumers . Apart from that, the texture of the cake mud sticky rice this black has special tenderness , giving experience sensory satisfaction for consumers . The resulting aroma , which is characteristic typical from sticky rice black , no only add mark sensory products, but also provide impression naturally inviting appetite .

In context health , cake mud sticky rice This gluten free black offers an attractive alternative for individuals who have intolerance to gluten or who choose a gluten- free diet as part of style their healthy life . With content higher nutrition and properties powerful antioxidant , cake this mud is not just a delicious snack , but it can also be support health body as a whole . Furthermore , there are research shows exists connection between diet and condition health , incl autism . A number of individuals with autism may have sensitivity to gluten or intolerance to certain ingredients in food. In this context , cake mud sticky rice black gluten free can be a suitable choice to fulfill need nutrition and food preferences of individuals with autism , while ensure that they Get food that is delicious and safe to consume . Thus , the results of this product development can also be achieved expand scope society can enjoy benefits , including people with autism.

Conclusion

Based on the research findings, several conclusions can be drawn:

1. Optimal Recipe Development:

The optimal recipe for making Black Sticky Rice Mud Cake involves using 100% black glutinous rice flour without mixing it with other types of flour. This substitution maintains the unique texture, flavor, and nutritional benefits of black glutinous rice, making it an ideal alternative for creating gluten-free products.

2. High Consumer Acceptance:

The acceptance rate for the Black Sticky Rice Mud Cake product reached 88.89%. This high acceptance rate indicates a positive response from the panelists, who found the overall sensory attributes—such as taste, texture, aroma, and appearance—satisfactory. This suggests strong market potential for the product among consumers seeking gluten-free options.

3. Packaging Recommendations:

To ensure the product's quality and appeal, it is recommended to package the Black Sticky Rice Mud Cake in transparent mica containers with lids. Additionally, the packaging should feature comprehensive labels that provide detailed information about the product, including its ingredients, nutritional content, and storage and consumption instructions. This information will help enhance consumer understanding and trust in the product.

4. Nutritional and Sensory Benefits:

Utilizing black glutinous rice flour not only makes the mud cake gluten-free but also enriches its nutritional profile with higher fiber, protein, and antioxidants, particularly anthocyanins. These attributes make the Black Sticky Rice Mud Cake a healthful choice for individuals with gluten intolerance or those who prefer a gluten-free diet.

5. Implications for Special Dietary Needs:

The development of this gluten-free mud cake offers a valuable food option for individuals with gluten-related disorders, such as celiac disease, non-celiac gluten sensitivity, and even for individuals with autism who may benefit from a gluten-free diet. The product thus serves a dual purpose of being both a nutritious snack and a safe dietary option for those with special dietary needs.

In conclusion, the Black Sticky Rice Mud Cake developed in this study demonstrates significant potential as a commercially viable gluten-free product, combining desirable sensory qualities with enhanced nutritional benefits. Further research and development can explore additional variations and enhancements to cater to a broader consumer base.

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